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Research Article

Prevention Of Cap Locking Problem in Syrups by Additives And pH Adjustment Method

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ABSTRACT

Background:Cap locking is a filling problem in sugar syrups. The sugar in the syrup crystallizes on the bottle cap and the threads, making it difficult to remove the cap. The study investigates the inhibition of sucrose crystallization on the bottleneck and cap of sugar syrup-containing products by treating them with various additives and buffers in the manufacturing process. **Methodology:** Simple syrup (66% w/w sucrose) and partially inverted syrup (in which 66% w/w sucrose was treated with Citric acid, Citric monohydrate, Sodium hydroxide, Buffers (with pH-4, pH-5, and pH-6)) were prepared and observed visually for the crystal growth by spreading on the open Petridishes, Bottle caps, and filled in syrup bottles which were kept at room temperature (25°C). Paracetamol syrup that prepared using simple syrup considered as control syrup product and that was prepared using Citric acid, Citric acid monohydrate, Sodium hydroxide and different buffers were considered as test syrups. The syrups were evaluated for presence of reduced sugars, Viscosity, Surface tension and specific rotation and also visual observation for crystal growth. The Ofners method was used to measure the amount of invert sugar. **Observation And Results:** No crystal growth was observed for the first 3 weeks in all the formulations. Later 3 weeks crystal growth was observed in the formulation containing citric acid and syrup with pH-6 buffer. No crystal growth was observed in the formulation containing Citric acid monohydrate, Sodium hydroxide and syrup with pH-5, and pH-8 buffers. Hence Paracetamol syrups were prepared by simple syrup, additives and buffers and no crystal growth was observed in the syrups with citric acid monohydrate and citro phosphate buffer of pH 5. **Conclusion:** The percentage of invert sugar in all the syrups was determined by Ofner's method and its viscosity, pH, specific rotation, Surface tension were also determined. The crystal growth was compared in the simple syrup and the invert syrups and observed inhibition of crystal growth in invert syrups prepared by using Citric acid,

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monohydrate and pH-5 citro-phosphate buffer. Hence the work has concluded that the caplocking can be prevented by adjusting pH and also by adding citric acid monohydrate during manufacturing process.

INTRODUCTION

Syrups are concentrated solutions of sugar (such as sucrose) in water or other aqueous liquids with or without added flavoring agents and medicinal substances Sucrose. Sucrose is the most widely used sweetener, with a long history of use. It is a white crystalline powder, soluble in water and alcohol. It inhibits the growth of m.o. in solution at concentrations above 65wt% by reducing the water-activity coefficient. Official simple syrup is an 85% w/v solution of sucrose in water. During

the preparation of sucrose solution, care should be taken to avoid charring and caramelization caused by heat. Sucrose is chemically and physically stable in the pH range of 4.0–8.0. It is frequently used in conjunction with sorbitol, glycerin, and other polyols, which reduce its tendency to crystallize. Sugar syrups promote significant “cap-locking”—the crystallization of the sugar on the cap and bottle thread, but the addition of glycerin (10–20%) minimizes this effect. Glycerin is seldom used as a single sweetener in pharmaceuticals because it has a characteristic mouth warming and burning effect.

Chemical reaction: 2

Fig1: Sucrose Hydrolysis

There is four steps occurring in crystallization: generation of a supersaturated phase nucleation, crystal growth and recrystallization. In the super saturated solution thermodynamic forces leads to crystal growth During nucleation, the molecules in the liquid state rearrange and eventually form into a stable cluster that organizes into a crystalline lattice. The ordered arrangement of molecules in the lattice involves a release of latent heat as the phase change occurs. Growth continues until all the supersaturated solution depleted and the system approaches an equilibrium. Once equilibrium in phase volume has been attained, changes still may take is called recrystallization.³

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Research works has been done on preventing crystallization of sucrose by treating with citric acid monohydrate and the Diphenhydramine hydrochloride syrup product manufactured by using sugar syrup where content of invert sugars is reduced to less than 15% w/w. (Heyam Ali etal) 4

MATERIALS

Sucrose purchased from the local market, Tagarapuvalasa, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India and the remaining chemicals were purchased from the Yarrow chemicals, Mumbai.

METHODS

Syrups were prepared with additives and buffers according to the formula given in the tables 1,2 and Paracetamol syrups were prepared according to the formula given in the table3

Table1: Formulation Table for Syrups with Additives

Syrup code	water	Sucrose	Citric acid monohydrate	Citric acid	Sodium hydroxide
SS	33.3g	66.6g	-	-	-
IS-CMA	33.3g	66.6g	0.022g	-	-
IS-CA	33.3g	66.6g	-	3g	-
IS-NaOH	33.3g	66.6g	-	-	0.67g

Table2: Formulation Table F Invert Syrups with Buffers

Syrup code	Sucrose	water	pH5Buffer	pH6 Buffer	pH8 Buffer
IS-pH5	66.6g	33.3g	Q. S	--	-
IS-pH6	66.6g	33.3g	-	Q. S	-
IS-pH8	66.6g	33.3g	-	-	Q. S
		33.3g			

Table3: Formulation of Paracetamol Syrups

Syrup code	water	Sucrose	Paracetamol	Citric acid monohydrate	pH 5
P-SS	33.3g	66.6g	2g	-	-
IS-PP1	33.3g	66.6g	2g	0.022g	-
IS-PP-2	33.3g	66.6g	2g	-	Q. S

Preparation of sugar syrup (66%w/w)⁵:

100 g of sugar syrup was prepared by heating 33.4 g of purified water to 70°C ±1°C in a syrup manufacturing vessel in a water bath. Then 66.6 g of sucrose was dissolved in the hot water in the manufacturing vessel with stirring. After that, the temperature was raised to 90°C ±1°C. At this temp, the sucrose solution was heated for 45 minutes. Then sugar syrup was cooled to 40°C. Finally weight of the sugar syrup was adjusted to 100 g with purified water and stirred for 2 minutes. Thus sugar syrup was prepared and considered as the control sample SS-1.

Preparation of partially inverted sugar syrup(66%w/w) with additives:

100 g of partially inverted sugar syrup was prepared by heating 33.3 g of purified water to 70°C ±1°C in a syrup manufacturing vessel in a water bath. The additives in the required quantity (as per the table)was dissolved in hot purified water in a manufacturing container. Then 66.6 g of sucrose was dissolved in the hot water in manufacturing vessel in stirring. After that, the temperature was raised to 90°C ±1°C. At this temp, the sucrose solution was heated for 45 minutes. Then the syrup(inverted) was cooled to 40°C. Finallythe weight of the inverted sugar syrup was

adjusted to 100g with purified water. Thus partially inverted sugar syrups were prepared.³All the inverted syrups were coded as per the table no **Preparation of partially inverted sugar syrup (66%w/w) with buffers^{6,7}** :

100g of partially inverted sugar syrup with buffers mentioned above were prepared. First, 33.3g of purified water was heated to $70^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a syrup manufacturing vessel in a water bath. Then 66.6 g of sucrose was dissolved in the hot water in the manufacturing vessel with stirring. Then the sucrose solution was heated at $90^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 minutes. Afterwards, the sugar syrup was cooled at 40°C . The final weight of the sugar syrup was adjusted to 100 g with buffers. The inverted syrups were observed visually for the crystal growth of sucrose for 6weeks and the results were given in the table Based on the results the Paracetamol syrups were prepared with citric acid mono hydrate, pH ,NaOH were prepared and evaluated for various parameters results were given in the table

Formulation of Paracetamol syrup with buffer PH-5⁸⁻¹³:

PART-1:

First, 10g of PEG-6000 was heated at 50°C . 2.5g of paracetamol was added to it, and the solution was stirred for 30 minutes. After that 2.5g of glycerin was heated at 50°C and then added to the above solution (PEG-6000+paracetamol) under continuous stirring. The solution was stirred until the transparent solution was obtained. After that, the above mixture was added to the hot purified

water under continuous stirring until the transparent solution was obtained.

Part-2:

Then 50g of partially inverted sugar syrup with pH-5 buffer-was prepared. First, 16.7 g of purified water was heated to $70^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a syrup manufacturing vessel in a water bath. Then 33.3 g of sucrose was dissolved in the hot water in the manufacturing vessel with stirring. Then the sucrose solution was heated at $90^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 minutes. Afterward, the sugar syrup was cooled at 40°C . The final weight of the sugar syrup was adjusted to 50 g with buffer PH-5.Slowly add part 1 to part 2 under continuous stirring. And it was labelled as IP-PP2.

Visual inspection of crystal growth on petridishes , Bottle necks and caps

The crystal growth was observed in syrups by pouring in petridishes and caps initially and after 6 week duration. The results were shown in the figures Based on the results the crystal growth was observed in simple syrup ,Syrups made with Citric acid and pH 6 buffer. There was no crystal growth in syrups made with citric acid monohydrate, NaOH and pH 5 buffer and these additives were chosen to prepare paracetamol syrups. After 6 weeks the paracetamol syrup(P-SS) has shown crystal growth in petridish and on bottle cap. The paracetamol syrup made with buffers(pH 6) and NaOH has not shown any crystal growth.

Fig2: Syrups in petridisheses initial

Fig3: Bottle caps initial

Fig4: Syrups in petridisheses initial

Fig5: Syrups in petridishes after 6 weeks

Fig6: Paracetamol syrups in petridishes (initial)

Fig7: Paracetamol syrup on bottle neck after 6 weeks

Evaluation¹⁴:

Biochemical tests: These tests were performed to identify the presence of sugars. following tests are performed

Benedict's test:

Mix equal volumes of Benedict's reagent and test solution in test solution in a test tube. Heat in boiling water bath for 5 mins. the solution appears green yellow or red colour depending on the

amount of reducing sugar present in the test solution.

The samples were passed and the results were given in the Table6.

Surface Tension:

The surface tension of the prepared syrups was measured using a stalagmometer and a specific gravity bottle. Results were given in Table6.

Specific Gravity:

The specific gravity of the prepared syrups was measured using the specific gravity bottle. Results are given in table 6.

Viscosity:

The viscosity of the syrups was measured using Ostwald's viscometer and calculated by using the formula given below. Results are given in the table 6.

pH:

pH Measurement using a pH Meter:

The pH of the prepared syrups was measured using a pH meter.

Results are given in the table 6.

Measurement of optical activity with Polarimeter¹⁴

After ensuring the equipment tube was clean, The instrument set up on the bench with the analyzer head facing the operator, an illuminated sodium lamp is attached with equipment through a bracket. The red indicator glowed on the transformer and then waited for 5 minutes for complete illumination of sodium vapor lamp. The position of the Sodium vapor lamp is such that the field can be seen clearly while viewing through the lower eyepiece. The lower eyepiece adjusted properly either towards or away from the eye to view clearly. After focusing on the upper eyepiece the scale graduation and a vertical line called the reference line were viewed. The sample was filled in the tube and placed in the polarimeter and viewed through the lower eyepiece and until match the colour shade to be similar in both sections by rotating the knob placed on the opposite to the eyepiece. Then the scale reading was measured and substituted in the equation to know the specific rotation value. The results were given in the table 8.

Determination of Reducing Sugars by the Modified Ofner Titrimetric method¹⁵⁻²⁰:

The complex formed between Cu^+ ions and potassium sodium tartrate is reduced by reducing sugars to univalent Cu^+ which is precipitated as Cu_2O . The precipitated Cu_2O is then determined by iodometric titration. The Cu_2O is oxidized by an excess is back titrated with sodium thiosulphate. The reaction between the reducing sugars and the Cu^{++} complex is not stoichiometric. The amount of Cu_2O formed depends upon the prescribed reaction conditions which therefore must be strictly followed. It has been determined that 1 ml of 0.01615 mol/l iodine solution is equivalent to 1mg of reducing sugars, once the correction for the reducing effect of sucrose has been taken into account.

Hot value:

After preparation of Ofner's solution 50ml of the Ofner's solution was mixed with 50 ml of each syrup (Simple syrup,) separately, some pumice pieces were added and boiled for 5 minutes cooled for 10 minutes after cooling 1ml concentrated acetic acid and iodine solutions were added until the solution turns blue colour. the excess iodine was back titrated with 10 to 15 ml sodium thiosulfate. 15ml 1M HCl added and titrated against 0.0333mol/l, 1ml of starch was added before the endpoint reached.

Cold value:

50 ml of each syrup was mixed with 50ml of Ofner's solution and the procedure given in hot value was repeated without heating and volume of iodine and sodium thiosulfate was noted.

Blank value:

50ml of water was added to 50ml of Ofner's solution and the procedure in hot value was repeated without heating and volumes of iodine and sodium thio sulfate were noted.

Expression of Results : the terms involved in calculation was explained in the table no 1 and results were given in table 4.

Table 4: Calculation of the Results by Ofners method

S. No		Amount Of Iodine For	Amount Of Thiosulphate For
1	Hot value	V ₁	V ₂
2	Cold value	V ₃	V ₄
3	Blank	V ₅	V ₆

Corrected consumption of 0.01667 mol/l iodine solution:

Calculated hot value, $A = (V_1 \times f_1) - (V_2 \times f_{Th})$

Calculated cold value, $B = (V_3 \times f_1) - (V_4 \times f_{th})$

Calculated blank value, $C = (V_5 \times f_1) - (V_6 \times f_{th})$

Invert sugar, mg/lcg = $(A - B - C - D) \times 1000 \times s$

where s = the amount of sample in 50 ml of prepared solution based on the calculation the amount of inverted sugar in all the syrups was measured and the results were given in the table 7.

SS-01	Negative	Absent
IS-CAM	Positive	Present
IS-CA	Positive	Present
IS-NaOH	Positive	Present
IS-pH-5	Positive	Present
IS-pH-6	Positive	Present
IS-pH-8	Positive	Present
IS-PSS	Negative	Absent
IS-PP1	Positive	Present
IS-PP2	Positive	Present

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 5: Results Of Bendicts Test

Syrup Code	Result	Inference (Reducing sugars)

The results from Bendicts test were given in the table 5 and these results indicated that all the syrups have reducing sugars except simple syrup.

Table 6: List Of Physical Properties of The Syrups

Syrup	Surface Tension(dy nes/cm)	pH	Viscosity (cps)	Density(g/ml)
SS-01	54.4	8.86	8.16	1.30
IS-CAM	49.8	5.82	5.76	1.25
IS-CA	57.8	5.64	7.12	1.26
IS-NaOH	53.5	9.25	6.01	1.28
IS-pH-5	64.3	5.81	5.08	1.29
IS-pH-6	57.4	6.96	6.00	1.27
IS-pH-8	63.3	7.92	5.57	1.27
IS-PSS	61.5	8.26	8.27	1.30
IS-PP1	59.3	6.33	6.74	1.28
IS-PP2	56.8	5.47	6.84	1.29

The viscosity, Surface tension, pH and specific gravity value of all the prepared syrups were given

in the table all the results meet the required specifications.

Ofner's Method Calculation:

Table 7: Results From Ofners Calculation

Syrup	Hot value	Cold value	Blank value	Sample value	Invert sugar concentration
IS-CAM	24.2	18.5	2.6	1.9	25.6
IS-NaOH	24.2	18.5	2.6	2	25.2
IS-CA	24.2	18.5	2.6	2.3	20
IS-pH-5	24.2	18.5	2.6	1.6	26.5

IS-pH-6	24.2	18.5	2.6	2.2	24.4
IS-Ph-8	24.2	18.5	2.6	1.5	18.3
IS-PP1	24.2	18.5	2.6	1.4	49.28
IS-PP2	24.2	18.5	2.6	2.5	24

Based on the ofners calculation it was concluded that the syrups has sufficient amount of invert sugar(20-50mg/l) which was necessary to prevent crystal growth.

Table 8 : Results from Polarimeter

Syrup	D-Glucose	D-Fructose	Specific rotation
IS-CAM	+51 ⁰	-85 ⁰	-17 ⁰
IS-PP1	+54 ⁰	-87 ⁰	-16.5 ⁰
IS-PP2	+54	-91	-18.5 ⁰

The specific rotation values indicated that the presence of invert sugar obtained by the hydrolysis of sucrose that can prevent crystallization and also the cap locking problem in the syrups.

CONCLUSION:

The above study concluded that the cap-locking problem in syrups due to crystal growth can be reduced by adding different additives like citric acid, citric acid monohydrated and NaOH and maintaining pH by the addition of buffers, the crystal growth in syrups is prevented by hydrolysing sucrose into glucose and fructose which leads to formation of invert syrup. The hydrolysis can be promoted by adding additives and also maintaining Ph. Initially a set of seven formulations was prepared and evaluated for the presence of reducing sugars and other parameters (density, viscosity, and surface tension). These syrups were tested by Ofner's method and polarimeter to measure the concentration of invert sugar. Among all the formulations the formulations contained CAM, NaOH and Ph-5 & pH-8 (IS-CAM, IS-NaOH, IS-Ph-5, IS-Ph-8) have not shown crystal growth even after 6 weeks based on the invert sugar content and crystal growth we have selected IS-CAM, IS-PH-5 for the incorporation of paracetamol. The paracetamol syrups were also evaluated for the mentioned parameters, Ofner's method and specific rotation by polarimeter. The work has concluded that cap-locking can be prevented by adding CAM(citric acid monohydrate) and Ph-5 citro-phosphate buffer.

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